
**THE EFFECT OF AGREEABLENESS ON INNOVATIVE BEHAVIOR
IN MILLENNIAL GENERATION EMPLOYEES IN THE SPECIAL
REGION OF YOGYAKARTA WITH KNOWLEDGE SHARING AS AN
INTERVENING VARIABLE**

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Abstract

The success of a company cannot be separated from the role of its human resources. In this era of digitalization and increasingly rapid technological developments, companies are required to always innovate. This research will examine the influence of agreeableness on innovative behavior with knowledge sharing as an intervening variable. Sampling in this study used purposive sampling technique with 60 respondents with the criteria of millennial generation employees aged 27-42 years who live and work in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The tests carried out in this research were instrument testing (validity test and reliability test), classical assumption test, hypothesis test (t test), coefficient of determination and path analysis using the Sobel test. The results of this research show that agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on innovative behavior, agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on innovative behavior and knowledge sharing partially mediates the influence of agreeableness on innovative behavior.

Keywords: Agreeableness, Knowledge Sharing, Innovative Behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

The era of digitalization and rapid technological development, businesses or companies should always be ready to adapt to all changes. However, there are still some companies that end up falling because they are unable to keep up with changes. Therefore, innovation is the main key for the company to survive and be able to compete in keeping up with the times. Innovation is important for companies to win the market and achieve sustainable development goals (Jada et al., 2019). During the innovation process, companies face challenges in terms of the ability of their human resources to carry out an innovation. Meanwhile, the innovation needed in the company cannot be separated from the role of human resources or individuals in it. So from human resources must have a qualified ability to innovate.

When innovating human resources are required to have innovative behavior in order to keep up with changes and achieve company goals (Ogbonnaya & Valizade, 2018). Therefore, companies need to create innovative behavior in their human resources so that the innovation process can occur. Innovative behavior is an individual action that can bring up, introduce and implement something new and beneficial to the organization (Wahyudi, 2020).

Innovative behavior in the workplace will increase if there is knowledge sharing in it. Innovative behavior and knowledge sharing are common situations in companies, but lack

of knowledge about the complete benefits of knowledge sharing makes companies not focus on its application (Rahmahthia & Ethics, 2019).

In the context of work, a person's personality is an important factor in knowledge sharing, therefore it is necessary to understand the characteristics of individual personality to know about how to share knowledge with others (Suryariana, 2012). The relationship between personality and knowledge sharing has been widely researched before, such as research conducted by there are two dimensions of Cabrera et al. (2006) The Big Five Personalities that affect knowledge sharing, namely agreeableness and openness to experience. In this study, researchers only focused on agreeableness. Someone who has high agreeableness tends to be cooperative, helpful and happy to help others. This character is thought to greatly influence someone to do knowledge sharing (Cabrera et al., 2006).

Individuals who agreeableness will also find it easy to generate, introduce and implement new things or creative ideas with others because they tend to actively share information to maintain positive relationships and like to socialize (Liu et al., 2018). This is supported by research that finds that agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on increasing innovation (Hamsani et al., 2020).

Individuals with low aggressiveness scores indicate weak efforts to improve cooperation and relationships with others. While in the context of innovation, effective and open collaboration to share ideas with others can produce better innovation (Hamsani et al., 2020). But this is not in line with research conducted by Mutaqin (2017) which found that agreeableness has no influence on innovative behavior. Therefore, this study wants to confirm the effect of agreeableness on innovative behavior.

Thus, employees who have a high agreeableness attitude can create a work atmosphere that supports knowledge sharing and facilitates innovative behavior, which in turn can strengthen productivity and creativity in the organization. This is evidenced by Sabrina (2020) research that has been conducted by and which found that Sabrina (2020) and Nurhidayati (2023) knowledge sharing acts as a mediating variable between agreeableness and innovation behavior. So it can be said that high agreeableness character and shown by knowledge sharing will affect better innovative behavior.

Gunadi (in Putri, 2020) states that the generation that is dominating the labor market in recent years is the millennial generation, this generation is predicted to grow even more in the next five years. The Millennial Generation or Generation Y is the demographic group after Generation X. Millennials are characterized as a creative, innovative and productive generation (Perdana, 2019). In the world of work, the millennial generation is faced with very high demands to understand and keep up with the times quickly. In addition, employees, in this case the millennial generation with their creative and innovative characters, are required to always bring up innovative behaviors that can create innovations that are useful for the company (Putri, 2020).

Based on the background description above, the main problem faced in this study is "How Millennial Generation employees can bring up innovative behavior that can create useful innovations for the company". While the objectives to be achieved in this study are to test and analyze the effect of agreeableness on innovative behavior through knowledge sharing on millennial generation employees in the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

TEORITICAL BACKGROUND

Agreeableness

According to Sukenik et al. (2018) agreeableness is one of the five main personality traits in the Big Five Personality Traits that measures the extent to which a person is considered generous, warm, friendly, and cooperative. Individuals who have an agreeableness personality tend to actively seek information that helps them maintain positive relationships, they also actively choose to expose themselves to other individuals who also like to socialize and collaborate (Liu et al., 2018). According to Costa and McCrae (in Nanda et al., 2020), there are six indicators in agreeableness, namely trust, straightforwardness, altruism, compliance, modesty, tendermindedness.

Knowledge Sharing

According to Mittal & Dhar (2015) knowledge sharing is the process of exchanging information owned by employees through interaction and communication. According to Tung (in Fikri and Laily, 2022) knowledge sharing is the process of sharing, disseminating, and exchanging information and knowledge between individuals to other individuals, individuals to groups, and also between groups to other groups to create new knowledge. According to Van Den Hooff & Ridder (in Rudiyanto 2012), there are 2 dimensions of knowledge sharing, namely bringing/donating knowledge and collecting knowledge. Indicators of bringing/donating knowledge are sharing new knowledge, sharing new information about work, attention to coworkers and sharing experiences, while indicators of Collecting Knowledge are asking for new information and asking for new skills.

Perilaku Inovatif

Innovative behavior is defined as all individual actions that lead to the emergence, introduction, and application of something new and profitable at all levels of the organization (Sulistiowati & Komari, 2021). According to De Jong & Den Hartog (2010), innovative behavior is a behavior possessed by individuals who have the aim of producing, introducing and implementing new things or creative ideas as well as the courage to take risks that can benefit the organization. Indicators of innovative behavior according to De Jong & Den Hartog (in Hadi et al., 2020) are opportunity exploration, idea generation, idea championing, and idea implementation.

HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

The Effect of Agreeableness on Knowledge Sharing

Agreeableness is a personality that describes a person's character tends to be easy to help, likes an attitude of trust and is friendly to establish an interpersonal relationship with other individuals (Grace dan Virlia, 2020). They are willing to listen and exchange opinions with others, are cooperative, and are able to create a harmonious work environment. Meanwhile, employees who score low on agreeableness are generally easily suspicious, stingy, unfriendly, unfriendly, easily annoyed, like to criticize others, more aggressive and less (Feist dan Feist 2008). So that the existence of an agreeableness personality can encourage the creation of knowledge sharing.

This is supported by research by penelitian Suryariana (2012);Matzler et al. (2008); Cabrera et al. (2006) which found a positive and significant influence between agreeableness on knowledge sharing. Cabrera et al. (2006) suggested that individuals who have a high score on agreeableness are considered as someone who is cooperative and supportive, so they will do knowledge sharing to other individuals, both in the form of

information, knowledge, experience, ideas and skills. So the higher the agreeableness score, the higher the tendency to do knowledge sharing. From the opinions above, the following hypothesis can be drawn:

H1: Agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing.

The Effect of Knowledge Sharing on Innovative Behavior

The existence of knowledge sharing allows an organization to generate new ideas that are used for the creation of innovation (Rozaq, 2014). Having a group capable of knowledge sharing makes employees feel more confident to convey creative ideas when completing work (Djazilan dan Darmawan, 2022). According to Rahab et al. (in Sulistiowati, 2018) Knowledge sharing that occurs between individuals involved in an organization will be able to create cooperation that gives and receives knowledge so that it can encourage innovation. Knowledge sharing can increase the ability to innovate and optimize the ability of human resources to find creative ideas.

According to Andre (in Mazidah dan Laily, 2020) The application of knowledge sharing can increase the ability to innovate employees in terms of generating and implementing new ideas or methods in the work process from the results of exchanging information or knowledge. This is in line with the research of Rozaq (2014) and Firmaiansyah et al. (2014) which found a positive and significant influence between knowledge sharing on innovation behavior. From the above opinions, a hypothesis can be drawn as follows:

H2: Knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on innovative behavior.

The Effect of Agreeableness on Innovative Behavior

According to Costa & McCrae (in Nurhidayati, 2023) Agreeableness is someone who has a high level of agreement, has a tendency to trust easily, be generous, obedient, easy to accept and behave well. Individuals with agreeableness tend to actively seek information to maintain positive relationships, like to socialize and collaborate with others. So that individuals who agreeableness will find it easy to produce, introduce and implement new things or creative ideas with others because they tend to actively seek information to maintain positive relationships and like to socialize (Liu et al., 2018). According to Hamsani et al. (2020) effective collaboration and being open to sharing ideas with others can lead to better innovation.

This is supported by the research of Hamsani et al. (2020) which found that agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on increasing innovation. However, research conducted by Mutaqqin (2017) found that agreeableness has no influence on innovative behavior. Therefore, this study wants to confirm the effect of agreeableness on innovative behavior.

H3: Agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Behavior.

The Effect of Agreeableness on Innovative Behavior Through Knowledge Sharing

Efforts to increase innovative behavior in an organization or company require knowledge sharing that occurs in the organization. Knowledge sharing allows an organization to generate new ideas that are used to create innovation (Rozaq, 2014). According to Fang Liu (in Sabrina, 2020) Individuals who have knowledge will do knowledge sharing if they have trust in other individuals. This shows that the level of trust, which is one of the indicators of agreeableness, can determine the level of knowledge sharing. So it can be concluded that agreeableness affects innovative behavior through knowledge sharing.

Research conducted by Suryariana (2012) found that agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, then Sabrina (2020) and Nurhidayati (2023) in

their research found that knowledge sharing is able to become an intervening variable (mediation) between agreeableness and innovation behavior. So it can be said that the influence of the character of agreeableness on innovation behavior will be more effective if it is through the knowledge sharing process. From the above opinions, the following hypothesis can be drawn:

H4: Knowledge sharing mediates the effect of agreeableness on innovative behavior.

Figure 1: Research Framework

METHODS

This study wants to see the effect of agreeableness on innovative behavior with knowledge sharing as an intervening variable. the population in this study are all millennial generation employees who live and work in Yogyakarta Special Region. The sampling technique used is non probability sampling with purposive sampling. The data used is primary data in the form of millennial generation perceptions obtained by 60 respondents.

This research is a field research or survey whose data acquisition method uses a questionnaire. The questionnaire is used by researchers as a research instrument to obtain data or information from respondents. The questionnaire used in this study is a questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale. The data analysis used consists of instrument tests, classical assumption tests, simple linear regression tests and sobel tests with the SPSS version 22 statistical program.

RESULTS

Validity and Reliability Test Results

The validity test results show that all statements from the three variables can be declared valid because they have a value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$ (0.254). The reliability test results of the three variables were declared reliable because they had a Cronbach's Alpha value (α) > 0.60 .

Classical Assumption Test Results

Normality Test

The regression model is good one that has a normal data distribution. Normality testing in this study uses Kolmogorov Smirnov, which results in a significant value of the three regression models of 0.200 which means more than ($>$) 0.05 so it can be concluded that the three data equation models tested are normally distributed. Thus the assumption of normality is met in all three models.

Linearity Test Results

Based on the results of the linearity test that has been carried out, it shows that the sig

deviation from linearity value of the three models is > 0.05 and the F count of the three models $< F$ table (4.01). So it can be concluded that the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable in each regression model is linear.

Heteroskedasticity Test Results

Based on the heteroscedicity test conducted using the scatter plot graph, it can be seen that the residual points spread randomly above and below the number 0 on the Y axis and do not form a certain pattern. Thus, homogeneity is met or there is no heteroscedicity in the three regression models.

Hypothesis Test Results

The t statistical test basically shows how far the influence of one explanatory / independent variable individually in applying variations in the dependent variable. This test uses a significant level of 5% or 0.05. T test is carried out with the criteria if $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ and significant value < 0.05 then there is an influence between the independent variable on the dependent variable Ghazali (2018). The results of the t statistical test that have been carried out using the help of the SPSS version 22 statistical program can be seen in the following table:

Tabel 1: Linear Regression Test Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	Sig	Information
X → Z	0,606	0,133	0,000	Significant
Z → Y	0,765	0,062	0,000	Significant
X → Y	0,668	0,092	0,000	Significant

Based on tab 1, the results of hypothesis testing in this study are as follows:

Testing the influence of agreeableness with knowledge sharing

The t statistical test results show that that the t value (5.805) $> t$ table (1.671) and a significant value of 0.000 $<$ Level of Significant (0.05). Thus there is a significant influence between Agreeableness on Knowledge Sharing. The constant value and coefficient show a positive direction, so it can be said that if the agreeableness variable increases, the knowledge sharing variable will also increase. So it can be concluded that H1 is accepted.

Testing the influence of knowledge sharing on innovative behavior

The t statistical test results show that that the t value (9.052) $> t$ table (1.671) and a significant value of 0.000 $<$ Level of Significant (0.05). Thus there is a significant influence between Knowledge Sharing on Innovative Behavior. The constant value and coefficient show a positive direction, so it can be said that if the knowledge sharing variable increases, the innovative behavior variable will also increase. So it can be concluded that H2 is accepted.

Testing the influence of agreeableness on innovative behavior

The t statistical test results show that that the t value (6.833) $> t$ table (1.671) and a significant value of 0.000 $<$ Level of Significant (0.05). Thus there is a significant influence between Agreeableness on Innovative Behavior. The constant value and coefficient show a positive direction, so it can be said that if the agreeableness variable increases, the innovative behavior variable will also increase. So it can be concluded that H3 is accepted.

Path Analysis (Sobel test)

Indirect influence *Agreeableness* (X) to Innovative Conduct (Y) through *Knowledge Sharing* (Z) produced by multiplying the regression coefficient $X \rightarrow Z$ and $Z \rightarrow Y$, which is as follows:

Indirect influence = (coefficient $X \rightarrow Z$) x (coefficient $Z \rightarrow Y$)

Indirect influence = $0.606 \times 0.765 = 0.463$

Based on the results of the calculation above, it can be seen that the direct influence is 0.668 and the indirect influence is 0.463. From the results of the calculations obtained, it shows the influence indirectly through *knowledge sharing* smaller than the direct influence of *agreeableness* towards innovative behavior. Thus it can be concluded that the variable *knowledge sharing* accepted as a partial mediation variable. Then to find out the significance of the mediating parameters will be tested using *Sobel Test* the following:

$a = 0.606$

$Sa = 0.133$

$b = 0.765$

$Sb = 0.062$

The standard calculation of the error of the indirect effect coefficient (Sab) is as follows:

$Sab = \sqrt{b^2 Sa^2 + a^2 Sb^2 + Sa^2 Sb^2}$

$Sab = \sqrt{(0,010352) + (0,001411) + (0,000067)}$

$Sab = \sqrt{(0,01183)}$

$Sab = 0.108765$

After knowing the results of the Sab , then the calculation of the t test is carried out to find out significant mediating parameters through the following formula:

$t = \frac{ab}{sab}$

$t = \frac{0,463}{0,108765}$

$t = 4.256$

Based on the results of the Sobel test above, a calculated t value of 4.256 can be obtained which is greater than the table t of 1.671 with a significant level of 0.05, meaning that the mediating parameter is significant. So it can be concluded that *knowledge sharing* mediates the influence of *agreeableness* on innovative behavior. Thus H4 is accepted.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Agreeableness on Knowledge Sharing

Based on the results of the first hypothesis test, it is known that the regression coefficient of the agreeableness variable is positive at 0.770, so that the agreeableness variable has a positive effect on knowledge sharing. Based on the partial test, a calculated t value of 5.805 is greater than the table t (1.671) and a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, so that H1 is accepted. These results show that as agreeableness increases, knowledge sharing will also increase or become better. On the other hand, as agreeableness decreases, knowledge sharing will also be lower. This research uses objects from millennial generation employees in D.I.Yogyakarta, which means that the higher the agreeableness personality possessed by millennial generation employees in D.I.Yogyakarta, the higher the knowledge sharing carried out where they work. The results of this research support previous research conducted by penelitan Suryariana (2012); Matzler et al. (2008); Cabrera et al. (2006), which shows the results that agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing.

The Effect of Knowledge Sharing on Innovative Behavior

The results of the second hypothesis test found that the regression coefficient of the knowledge sharing variable was positive at 0.566, so that the knowledge sharing variable had a positive effect on innovative behavior. Based on the partial test, a calculated t value of 9.052 is greater than the table t (1.671) and a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on innovative behavior, so that H2 is accepted. These results show that the more knowledge sharing increases, the more innovative behavior will also increase or become better. Conversely, the more knowledge sharing decreases, the lower innovative behavior will be. This research uses objects from millennial generation employees at D.I.Yogyakarta, which means that the higher the knowledge sharing behavior carried out by millennial generation employees at D.I.Yogyakarta, the higher the innovative behavior carried out where they work. The results of this research support previous research conducted by Rozaq (2014) and Firmaiansyah et al. (2014), which shows that there is a significant positive influence between knowledge sharing on innovation behavior.

The Effect of Agreeableness on Innovative Behavior

The results of the third hypothesis test found that the regression coefficient of the agreeableness variable was positive at 0.627, so that the agreeableness variable had a positive effect on innovative behavior. Based on the partial test, a calculated t value of 6.833 is greater than the table t (1.671) and a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on innovative behavior, so that H3 is accepted. These results show that as agreeableness increases, innovative behavior will also increase or become better. Conversely, as agreeableness decreases, innovative behavior will also be lower. This research uses objects from millennial generation employees in D.I.Yogyakarta, which means that the higher the agreeableness personality possessed by millennial generation employees in D.I.Yogyakarta, the higher the innovative behavior carried out where they work. The results of this research are supported by research conducted by Hamsani et al. (2020) who found that agreeableness had a positive and significant effect on increasing innovation. However, the results of this study are not in line with research conducted by Mutaqqin (2017) which found that agreeableness had no influence on innovative behavior.

Knowledge Sharing Mediates the Effect of Agreeableness on Innovative Behavior

The calculation results show that the direct influence of agreeableness on innovative behavior is 0.668 and the indirect influence of agreeableness on innovative behavior through knowledge sharing is 0.463. Thus, the indirect influence through knowledge sharing is smaller than the direct influence of agreeableness on innovative behavior. Thus it can be concluded that the knowledge sharing variable is accepted as a partial mediation variable. Then also obtained a calculated t value of 4.256 more than t table 1.671 with a significant level of 0.05. This indicates that the mediating parameters are significant. So it can be concluded that knowledge sharing mediates the influence of agreeableness on innovative behavior, thus H4 is accepted.

The results of this study found that knowledge sharing acts as a mediating variable between agreeableness and innovative behavior. So it can be said that the influence of agreeableness personality on innovative behavior will be more effective through knowledge sharing. This research uses objects from millennial generation employees in D.I.Yogyakarta, which means that, if millennial generation employees in D.I.Yogyakarta

have a high agreeableness personality, and this is demonstrated by carrying out knowledge sharing, this will influence better innovative behavior. The results of this research are supported by research conducted by Sabrina (2020) and Nurhidayati (2023) who found that knowledge sharing can be an intervening (mediation) variable between agreeableness and innovation behavior.

CONCLUSION

The results of this research show that agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on innovative behavior, agreeableness has a positive and significant effect on innovative behavior and knowledge sharing partially mediates the influence of agreeableness on innovative behavior. Companies are expected to choose employees who have high agreeableness characters during the recruitment process so that a culture of knowledge sharing within the company can be created, so that the innovative behavior of employees can also increase.

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